

Viscosities and Partial Molar Volumes of Tetramethyl Ammonium Chloride in Ethyl alcohol-Water Mixtures

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In order to investigate the ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions¹⁻⁴, viscosities and partial molar volumes from density measurements of tetramethylammonium chloride solution in various ethanol-water mixtures and at various temperatures have been measured.

Results and Discussion

An overall increase in viscosity was observed for compositions upto 60% ethanol (Fig. 1) and beyond which viscosity decreases. As the per-

centage of ethanol in the composition increases, viscosity increases due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between alcohol and water molecules as the molecular entities of type $(\text{EtOH})_m(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ ($m \geq n$ ($m, n > 1$)) are formed. With the further addition of ethanol in the composition, the viscosity decreases due to dilution effect.

The impact of solute on viscosity may be understood in terms of Grunberg and Nissan⁵ equation,

$$\ln \eta_{\text{mix}} = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d' \quad (1)$$

where η_{mix} , η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the mixture, ethanol and water respectively, x_1 and x_2 the mole fractions of the two components, d' is proportional to w/RT when w is the interchange energy⁶ or a measure of interactions. It is seen that the value of d' and excess viscosities are positive, suggesting complex formation involving solvent⁷. The interaction energy decreases with increasing percentage of ethanol as is evident from Fig. 1.

The relative viscosities have been analysed by Jones-Dole equation⁴,

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. The applicability of Jones-Dole equation was observed for the data. The positive values of A , the Falken-Hagen⁸ coefficient indicate that strong ion-ion interaction may presumably be, due to

Fig 1 Plots of d' as a function of percentage of (I) ethanol and (II) temperature and (III) plot of η vs percentage of ethanol

TABLE 1—LEAST-SQUARES FIT PARAMETER OF EQUATION (3)

Temp. °C	10% ethanol			20% ethanol			30% ethanol		
	A	B	S.D.	A	B	S.D.	A	B	S.D.
25	0.060	0.446	0.019	0.046 2	0.439	0.023	0.023 9	0.236	0.018
30	0.050	0.719	0.034	0.027 5	0.515	0.019	0.063 2	0.447	0.027
35	0.075 9	0.681	0.057	0.049 5	0.553	0.020	0.039	0.391	0.024
40	0.021 1	0.569	0.025	0.055 2	0.655	0.025	0.046 7	0.508	0.014
45	0.069 9	0.863	0.023	0.086	0.627	0.049	0.029 8	0.542	0.019
	40% ethanol			50% ethanol			60% ethanol		
25	0.049 7	0.363	0.019	0.024 6	0.281	0.002	0.019 5	0.196	0.012
30	0.047 5	0.423	0.038	0.067 1	0.420	0.022	0.002 7	0.305	0.011
35	0.045 6	0.448	0.022	0.040 1	0.382	0.018	0.056 3	0.402	0.038
40	0.070 8	0.516	0.033	0.046 5	0.426	0.016	0.043 3	0.389	0.010
45	0.047 2	0.591	0.027	0.040 2	0.402	0.019	0.048 5	0.493	0.025
	70% ethanol			80% ethanol			90% ethanol		
25	0.021 9	0.464	0.016	0.021 9	0.236	0.010	0.042 8	0.336	0.038
30	0.050 4	0.404	0.024	0.045 8	0.415	0.016	0.058 4	0.494	0.037
35	0.048 4	0.441	0.019	0.115	0.482	0.052	0.080 7	0.600	0.019
40	0.070 8	0.402	0.023	0.054 5	0.584	0.030	0.091 6	0.540	0.033
45	0.029 8	0.685	0.007	0.036 2	0.461	0.012	0.079	0.707	0.050

unusual cation-cation and cation-anion interactions, while positive values of *B* indicate that these interactions are strong enough and the extent of interaction is unaffected by the amount of ethanol. The values are given in Table 1.

The concentration dependence of apparent molar volumes has been explained in terms of Masson's equation⁹,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^o + S_v^* \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v^o is the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and S_v^* is the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^o , S_v^* , alongwith standard errors, are listed in Table 2. The positive and large values of S_v^* indicate the presence of strong ion-ion interactions. The decrease in ϕ_v^o values for all the compositions indicate the presence of solvent-solvent interactions³, and the increase in the S_v^* values indicates formation of complex ions.

TABLE 2—COMPUTED PARAMETERS OF EQUATION (3)

Temp. °C	10% ethanol			20% ethanol			30% ethanol		
	ϕ_v^o	S_v^*	S.D.	ϕ_v^o	S_v^*	S.D.	ϕ_v^o	S_v^*	S.D.
25	95.20	19.76	2.43	58.61	26.33	3.31	88.24	39.37	3.01
30	94.43	21.26	1.94	61.25	22.29	1.21	89.53	36.99	1.31
35	88.72	35.14	1.90	77.85	18.34	3.66	89.83	36.99	2.29
40	76.67	60.83	3.20	89.72	15.82	2.77	94.88	21.41	2.51
45	67.04	83.84	1.33	93.29	15.61	1.70	96.40	18.14	1.07
	40% ethanol			50% ethanol			60% ethanol		
25	80.05	54.26	3.13	106.7	30.47	1.68	97.51	15.16	1.77
30	77.67	63.13	1.10	103.38	32.82	2.87	96.94	16.74	2.24
35	75.27	60.42	1.81	94.18	38.20	2.35	94.99	17.99	3.50
40	72.04	67.28	2.92	93.28	39.69	1.87	90.25	18.79	3.27
45	70.62	68.36	1.16	78.32	43.88	1.84	81.00	20.08	1.58
	70% ethanol			80% ethanol			90% ethanol		
25	78.21	35.07	1.79	66.28	32.37	3.85	48.34	24.33	2.41
30	70.32	37.29	3.01	60.38	36.63	2.60	35.95	25.17	1.28
35	62.66	43.19	3.06	52.67	41.82	0.51	29.75	33.79	3.89
40	57.24	45.78	2.20	47.62	44.52	3.64	28.59	35.1	1.32
45	50.07	48.6	1.78	39.05	46.85	1.78	24.04	39.07	2.47

$\Delta\mu_2^{\circ*}$, the contribution per mole of solute to the free energy of activation for viscous flow of the solution, has been determined using equation (4) as suggested by Feakings *et al.*¹⁰,

$$B = \frac{\bar{v}_1^{\circ} - \bar{v}_2^{\circ}}{1000} + \frac{\bar{v}_1^{\circ}}{1000} \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{\circ*} - \Delta\mu_1^{\circ*}}{RT} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{v}_1^{\circ}$ and $\bar{v}_2^{\circ}$ are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ*}$, the free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent, is given by equation (5),

$$\Delta\mu_1^{\circ*} = RT \ln \left(\frac{\eta_1 \bar{v}_1^{\circ}}{Nh} \right) \quad (5)$$

for the mixed solvents. Each solvent mixture was treated as a pure solvent and the molar volume was taken as a mean value, which is defined as

$$\bar{v}_1^{\circ} = (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / \rho \quad (6)$$

where x_1 , M_1 and x_2 , M_2 are mole fractions and molecular weights of water and ethanol respectively, and ρ is the density of the solvent mixtures. The activation parameters for viscous flow of the electrolyte are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ*}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ*}$, $\Delta H^{\circ*}$, $T\Delta S^{\circ*}$ IN ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol % (by wt.)	$\Delta\mu_1^{\circ*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\mu_2^{\circ*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{\circ*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$T\Delta S^{\circ*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
10	16.26	13.49	422.3	408.8
20	16.44	15.41	457.5	442.0
30	16.64	18.93	520.7	401.7
40	16.76	20.71	540.7	519.9
50	16.78	26.75	552.4	525.6
60	17.00	33.56	571.9	538.3
70	16.96	26.96	508.3	481.3
80	16.93	23.25	457.5	434.2
90	16.92	19.07	376.7	357.6

It is evident from Table 3 that $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ*}$ is practically constant in all solvent compositions. This implies that B coefficient is dependent mainly on $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ*}$ and $(\bar{v}_1^{\circ} - \bar{v}_2^{\circ})$ terms. $\Delta H^{\circ*}$ and

$T\Delta S^{\circ*}$ are highly positive, thus the formation of the transition state is less favourable. The results suggest that the activated state is reached by bond-breaking and distortion of intermolecular bonds.

Experimental

Tetramethylammonium chloride (A.R. grade; purified¹¹), ethanol and double-distilled water were used. Ethanol-water mixture of varying compositions as well as solutions of the electrolyte were made by weight within accuracy of 0.2 mg. Density and viscosity measurements were done using a pycnometer and a Cannon-Ubbelohd viscometer respectively. The details of the experimental procedure are similar to that reported earlier².

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) was calculated from the density data using equation (7),

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_1 - d)}{Cd_1} + \frac{M_2}{d_1} \quad (7)$$

where C is molarity, d_1 and d are densities of the solvent and solution respectively, and M_2 is the molecular weight of the electrolyte.

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